

BOOKLET ON LANGUAGE LEARNING ARTICULATION DEVELOPMENT (BOOKLLAD): ENHANCING READING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Reading proficiency is crucial for academic success, yet many early secondary students struggle with key components like phonics, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency, hindering their progress and future opportunities. To address this, the Booklet on Language Learning Articulation Development (BOOKLLAD) was designed as an intervention to improve reading skills among Grade 7 learners. This study employed a pretest-posttest experimental design to evaluate BOOKLLAD's effectiveness at Maila Paderes Aritalla National High School in Jaguimitan, Passi City, Iloilo, during the 2023-2024 school year. Twenty-six students participated in a 20-day intervention, with a researcher-developed test assessing phonics, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency. The instrument's reliability was validated through Cronbach's Alpha and expert review. Data analysis using SPSS included frequency counts, means, standard deviations, and the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test. The findings revealed significant improvements, with average pre-intervention scores rising to above-average post-intervention. The statistically significant differences between pretest and posttest scores confirm BOOKLLAD's effectiveness in enhancing reading skills. The results align with theories like Schema Theory, Cognitive Load Theory, and the Zone of Proximal Development, highlighting the impact of structured, scaffolded, and personalized learning activities on reading comprehension and retention. The study emphasizes the importance of active engagement, scaffolded support, and customized learning in reading instruction and recommends that the Department of Education develop targeted programs to encourage

innovative teaching approaches. BOOKLLAD demonstrates significant potential as a tool for improving reading skills in Grade 7 students.

Keywords: *BOOKLLAD, Reading skills, Grade 7 learners, Language learning*

INTRODUCTION

Reading proficiency is a crucial component of academic success, and schools must address this foundational skill to ensure that learners can effectively engage with the broader curriculum. Students who lack the necessary reading skills often struggle to comprehend other subjects, leading to a cycle of poor performance that can negatively impact their overall well-being. This issue has been exacerbated by the recent shift to distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, where restrictions on face-to-face classes necessitated the use of printed modules. While essential during this period, these modules did not fully address the learning gaps, particularly among struggling readers. In Junior High School, these gaps have manifested as significant difficulties in reading and comprehension, persisting even as in-person classes resumed.

In 2023, oral reading assessments conducted by teacher advisers revealed that many students, especially in Grades 7 through 10, were reading at levels significantly below their grade. These students faced challenges in letter and word recognition, articulation, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency. Additional assessments showed that 96% of Grade 7 students and 78% of students from Grades 7-10 were at a frustration level in reading comprehension. Despite the introduction of various reading programs and interventions mandated by the Department of Education (DepEd), these challenges persisted, highlighting the need for more effective and targeted solutions.

To address these gaps, the "Booklet on Language Learning Articulation Development (BOOKLLAD): Enhancing Reading Skills" was developed as an innovative intervention. BOOKLLAD aims to provide learners with a structured and engaging framework for improving reading skills, specifically focusing on articulation, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency. Unlike video-based interventions, which have been shown to enhance reading comprehension through multimedia engagement (Gabor and Celeste, 2024), BOOKLLAD leverages the traditional yet effective medium of print. The booklet format is designed to provide a tangible, accessible, and self-paced learning resource that can be easily integrated into daily classroom activities or used independently by students. While video-based materials engage learners through visual and auditory stimuli, BOOKLLAD emphasizes the hands-on, interactive nature of print, which allows students to engage with the material at their own pace, fostering deep comprehension and retention.

The Department of Education has identified deficiencies in reading comprehension as a critical factor contributing to low achievement levels in core subjects like English, Math, and Science (DepEd, 2023). In this context, the BOOKLLAD program was

implemented at Maila Paderes Aritalla National High School to improve the reading proficiency of Grade 7 learners. The program aligns with Republic Act No. 9155, the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, which encourages educators to develop school-based projects that enhance the teaching-learning process (Republic Act No. 9155, 2001).

BOOKLLAD draws on theories of language acquisition, literacy development, and educational psychology, adopting a holistic approach to language learning. It recognizes the interconnectedness of articulation and reading, guiding learners through targeted activities to develop clear pronunciation alongside reading fluency, comprehension, and vocabulary. By examining the effectiveness of BOOKLLAD in enhancing reading skills, this study contributes to the existing literature on literacy education and provides practical insights for educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers. Ultimately, the goal is to empower learners with the linguistic competencies necessary for academic success and to thrive in a diverse and multilingual world.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effect of Booklet on Language Learning Articulation Development (BOOKLLAD) in teaching Grade 7 learners at Maila Paderes Aritalla National High School year 2023-2024.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the Pretest performance of the respondents?
2. What is the Posttest performance of the respondents?
3. Is there a significant difference in the Pretest and Posttest reading performance of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study and Respondents

This research was conducted in a public secondary school in Passi City, Iloilo, during the 2023-2024 academic year. The study focused on Grade 7 learners, who were selected using a purposive sampling method based on their reading proficiency levels. A total of 26 students participated in the study, all of whom were identified as needing improvement in key reading areas, including phonics, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency. The demographic details of the respondents, such as age and gender, were consistent with typical Grade 7 students in the Philippines, generally ranging from 12 to 13 years old.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research utilized a pretest-posttest experimental design, which is well-suited for measuring changes resulting from an intervention. The study began with securing

necessary permissions from relevant authorities and obtaining consent from the participants. The procedure was as follows:

Pretest: A baseline assessment was conducted to gauge the initial reading skills of the participants using a researcher-made reading assessment tool.

Intervention: The 20-day BOOKLLAD intervention was administered. This intervention included a series of structured activities focused on improving phonics, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency. The intervention was designed to be engaging and scaffolded, with each activity building on the previous one to reinforce learning and improve articulation.

Posttest: After the intervention, a posttest was conducted using the same assessment tool to measure any changes in the students' reading skills.

Research Instruments

The primary instrument used in this study was a researcher-developed reading assessment tool. This tool was designed to measure key components of reading proficiency, including phonics/sound recognition, vocabulary, comprehension, and fluency. The instrument consisted of multiple items, each targeting different aspects of reading skills. It was validated by experts in the field of education and literacy, and a pilot test was conducted to ensure its reliability. The instrument achieved a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.890, indicating a high level of internal consistency.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize the data and provide an overview of the respondents' reading skills. For the inferential analysis, the paired samples Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test was employed. This non-parametric test is appropriate for comparing related samples, particularly when the data do not necessarily follow a normal distribution. The test compared the pretest and posttest scores to determine the statistical significance of the changes observed.

Scope and Limitations

This study was limited to a small sample size of 26 students from a single public secondary school, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other populations. The intervention period was relatively short, spanning only 20 days, which may also affect the long-term retention of the reading skills gained. Additionally, while the study focused on key components of reading proficiency, it did not account for other factors that might influence reading development, such as socio-economic background or home literacy environment. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the

effectiveness of structured reading interventions like BOOKLLAD in improving specific reading skills among early secondary students.

RESULTS

Pretest Performance of Grade 7 Learners.

The average pretest score of 27.69 suggested that, initially, Grade 7 learners at Maila Paderes Aritalla National High School had a moderate level of proficiency in language learning and articulation development.

Table 1

The Pretest Performance of the Respondents

Category	Mean	SD	Description
Pretest	27.69	9.21	Average

Note: The scores were described using the following scale and description: (48.01 – 60.00) Excellent, (36.01 – 48.00) Above Average, (24.01 – 36.00) Average, (12.01 – 24.00) Below Average, (0.00 – 12.00) Poor

Posttest Performance of the Grade 7 Learners

The posttest results of the study revealed that the mean score of the respondents was 40.38 with a standard deviation of 7.46, categorizing their performance as “Above Average” according to the scoring scale used.

Table 2

The Posttest Performance of the Respondents

Category	Mean	SD	Description
Post Test	40.38	7.46	Above Average

Note: The scores were described using the following scale and description: (48.01 – 60.00) Excellent, (36.01 – 48.00) Above Average, (24.01 – 36.00) Average, (12.01 – 24.00) Below Average, (0.00 – 12.00) Poor

The Differences in the Pre-test and Post-test Performances of the Respondents

The Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test results indicated a significant improvement ($p = 0.000$) in the performances of Grade 7 learners from the pre-test to the post-test phase, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3

The Wilcoxon-Signed Rank Tests for the Significance of the Differences in the Pre-test and Post-test Performances of the respondents

Compared Variables	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Z	Sig.
Group (Experimental Pretest and Posttest)				4.439***	.000
Negative Ranks	1	1.00	1.00		
Positive Ranks	25	14.00	350.00		
Ties	0				
Total	26				

p*** < 0.001

DISCUSSION

The Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test results indicated a significant improvement ($p = 0.000$) in the performances of Grade 7 learners from the pretest to the posttest phase, as shown in Table 3. This statistical finding supported the rejection of the null hypothesis, suggesting that there was indeed a meaningful difference in the students' reading comprehension abilities following the implementation of the Booklet on Language Learning Articulation Development (BOOKLLAD) intervention. The observed improvement underscored the effectiveness of structured interventions like BOOKLLAD in enhancing students' language learning and articulation skills (Sadiku, 2015). Such interventions were crucial in addressing the challenges highlighted in previous studies, including the impact of global school closures on educational outcomes (de Vera, 2022) and the persistent issues in reading proficiency among Filipino students (San Juan, 2019; UNICEF). Moreover, the significant difference in pretest and posttest performances aligned with research emphasizing the complex nature of reading comprehension and its essential role in academic success (Helardez, 2021; Tomas et al., 2021). These findings highlighted the importance of targeted strategies in improving reading proficiency, thereby supporting overall student development and academic achievement (Block & Israel, 2005; McKown & Barnett, 2007; Alghonaim, 2020). Furthermore, the positive outcomes of the BOOKLLAD intervention reflected the effectiveness of structured language learning approaches and the importance of teacher facilitation in enhancing student comprehension (Singhal, 2001; Alyousef, 2006). By addressing specific reading comprehension challenges identified in previous studies (Vertucio, 2019; Albdour, 2015), interventions like BOOKLLAD contributed significantly to bridging educational gaps and fostering comprehensive student learning experiences.

Future studies could further investigate the specific impact of BOOKLLAD on different aspects of language learning, including speaking, reading, and writing skills.

Longitudinal studies could also track the progress of students over time to assess the sustainability and effectiveness of such interventions beyond immediate improvements observed in pretest and posttest comparisons.

Conclusions

The conclusions drawn from this study highlight the significant impact of the Booklet on Language Learning Articulation Development (BOOKLLAD) on improving the reading skills of Grade 7 students at Maila Paderes Aritalla National High School. Initially, the pretest results categorized the students' reading abilities as average, indicating a basic proficiency in fundamental skills such as decoding, comprehension, and vocabulary. However, this average performance also revealed notable gaps in more advanced reading strategies, critical analysis, and deeper textual understanding, underscoring the need for targeted intervention.

The introduction of BOOKLLAD as an instructional tool proved to be highly effective, as evidenced by the substantial improvement in the students' posttest performance. The students advanced from an average to an above-average level in their reading skills, demonstrating the program's ability to address both foundational and advanced literacy needs. This outcome not only validates the program's approach but also highlights its potential to serve as a key component in educational strategies aimed at enhancing reading proficiency.

The study's findings provide compelling evidence of BOOKLLAD's success in fostering significant gains in literacy among early secondary students. The statistically significant differences between the pretest and posttest scores confirm the program's efficacy and suggest that such interventions can play a crucial role in overcoming literacy challenges. As such, the continued implementation and expansion of BOOKLLAD could further enhance students' reading abilities, leading to improved academic performance across subject areas and contributing to their overall educational development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations can be made for different stakeholders:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials. The findings of this study offered valuable insights that can guide DepEd officials in developing targeted programs and training initiatives within the English curriculum. By integrating the effective teaching strategies identified in this research, DepEd can enhance professional development opportunities for teachers, focusing on areas such as active engagement techniques and scaffolded support. Furthermore, the study highlighted the importance of tailored interventions to address specific learning needs, promoting a more inclusive and impactful educational environment across schools nationwide.

Teachers. For educators, the results of this study served as a catalyst for innovation and professional growth. Armed with evidence-based practices from the BOOKLLAD intervention, teachers can refine their instructional approaches to foster deeper engagement and comprehension among students. Incorporating structured reading activities and personalized learning experiences can enhance teaching effectiveness, ultimately creating more enriching classroom experiences that cater to diverse learning styles and abilities.

English Teachers. This study presented an opportunity for English teachers to explore and implement novel methodologies aimed at improving language learning outcomes. By leveraging the findings, English teachers can integrate innovative teaching strategies into their lessons, such as schema theory-based activities and cognitive load management techniques. This approach not only enhanced students' language proficiency but also cultivated critical thinking and analytical skills necessary for academic success in English.

Researchers. For researchers in the field of education, this study offered a practical application of theoretical frameworks and research methodologies. Engaging with the BOOKLLAD intervention provided researchers with hands-on experience in educational intervention studies, contributing to the advancement of knowledge in effective teaching practices. Moreover, the study equipped researchers with insights into the practical implications of their theoretical knowledge, supporting future studies and academic contributions in educational research.

Learners. Students benefited directly from the outcomes of this study through enhanced educational practices and tailored learning experiences. By integrating evidence-based strategies into the curriculum, learners receive targeted support that fosters their academic growth and development. The findings informed educators and policymakers on effective approaches to teaching reading skills, ensuring that students receive a quality education that prepares them for lifelong learning and future endeavors.

Future Researchers. This study served as a foundational resource for future researchers interested in exploring similar topics or expanding upon the findings presented. By documenting the effectiveness of the BOOKLLAD intervention, this research provided a reference point for further investigation into educational interventions and their impact on student outcomes. Future researchers can build upon these insights, contributing to ongoing inquiry and innovation in educational practices, thereby advancing the field and improving educational outcomes globally.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, the researchers maintained strict adherence to ethical standards throughout the entire research process. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose and procedures. Participants were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative repercussions. Anonymity was

rigorously upheld, with all personal identifiers removed to protect the identities of the participants.

The researchers always safeguarded the well-being of the respondents, ensuring that their participation did not cause any harm or distress. There were no conflicts of interest influencing the conduct of the study, and the researchers ensured that all findings were presented objectively and without bias. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, with all sources and references appropriately cited.

The results of the study were utilized solely for academic and research purposes, contributing to the understanding of the effectiveness of the Booklet on Language Learning Articulation Development (BOOKLLAD) in enhancing reading skills among Grade 7 learners. Through these measures, the researchers ensured the highest standards of ethical integrity in the study.

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